

MACHINE LEARNING FOR EARLY HEART DISEASE DETECTION

Anuoluwapo O. Aleem*¹, Chukwudi S. Ubah*², Simon S. Adeleke*³

*^{1,3}Department Of Statistics And Data Science, Fox School Of Business, Temple University, Philadelphia, PA USA.

*²Department Of Public Health, Brody School Of Medicine, East Carolina University, Greenville, NC, USA.

DOI : <https://www.doi.org/10.56726/IRJMETS61879>

ABSTRACT

Heart disease has been proven to be the leading cause of death for both men and women, killing about 697,000 people in the US in 2020, which makes it a major concern to be dealt with. Identifying heart disease in patients could be quite challenging due to several contributory risk factors, which requires some high level of techniques. Machine learning proves to be effective in predicting heart disease in patients given the contributory risk factors. In this study, we used seven different machine learning algorithms such as K-Nearest Neighbors, support vector machine, Decision Tree, Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Neural Network, and AdaBoost, to predict whether a person has heart disease using the Cleveland Heart Disease Dataset from the UCI Repository. Our goal was to identify the most accurate algorithm for this task. Linear support vector machine (SVM) and Elastic net logistic regression have the best overall performance with an overall performance of 89%. These findings highlight the potential of machine learning in effectively improving heart disease diagnosis and management, offering promising avenues for improving patient care and outcomes.

Keywords: Heart Disease Diagnosis, K-Nearest Neighbors, Support Vector Machine, Decision Tree, Random Forest, Adaboost, Neural Network.

I. INTRODUCTION

Heart disease, also referred to as cardiovascular disease (CVD), encompasses a range of conditions affecting the heart and blood vessels. It stands as a formidable global health challenge, responsible for a significant portion of morbidity and mortality worldwide. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), cardiovascular diseases are the leading cause of death globally, with an estimated 17.9 million deaths in 2019, representing 32% of all global deaths [1]. Understanding the multifaceted nature of heart disease requires exploration into its various forms, risk factors, diagnostic approaches, and preventive strategies.

Coronary Artery Disease (CAD) is among the most prevalent forms of heart disease. It occurs when the coronary arteries, responsible for supplying blood to the heart muscle, become narrowed or obstructed due to the buildup of plaque. This condition restricts blood flow to the heart, leading to symptoms such as angina (chest pain) or potentially fatal events like heart attacks. Usually, it entails the development of plaques within the coronary arteries, hindering blood flow. It stands as the major cause of mortality both in the US and globally [2]. While it was an uncommon cause of death at the outset of the 20th century, fatalities attributed to CAD reached their peak in the mid-1960s before declining. Nonetheless, it remains the leading cause of death worldwide [3]. Heart failure, another common manifestation of heart disease, results from the heart's inability to pump blood effectively. Symptoms of heart failure include fatigue, shortness of breath, and fluid retention, often stemming from conditions like CAD, high blood pressure, or previous heart attacks [4].

Arrhythmia is a prevalent type of heart disease resulting from a broad spectrum of disorders of heart rate and rhythm abnormalities. These disruptions in the heart's electrical activity can cause the heart to beat too fast (tachycardia), too slow (bradycardia), or irregularly. Arrhythmia affects millions of individuals worldwide, with common symptoms including rapid or irregular heartbeat, shortness of breath, dizziness, chest pain, fatigue, and weakness. While some arrhythmias pose minimal risk, others, such as Atrial Fibrillation or Ventricular Fibrillation, can be life-threatening and increase the likelihood of stroke or heart attacks. Treatment options vary, and early diagnosis significantly improves prognosis, reducing the risk of sudden cardiac events [5,6].

Valvular heart disease is a significant cause of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality globally, with its impact expected to grow in the coming years. The heart's four valves—tricuspid, pulmonic, mitral, and aortic—are essential for preventing backward blood flow and maintaining necessary pressure gradients for effective

circulation. Valvular heart disease can cause regurgitation or stenosis, leading to backward blood flow or increased pressure behind the blockage, respectively, which disrupts cardiovascular function [7,8]. Accurate epidemiological data is crucial for designing effective public health interventions, but current global data often underestimates the prevalence of valvular heart disease due to limited access to diagnostic tools and underreporting, especially in developing countries and underserved populations [9,10].

The development of heart disease is influenced by a variety of risk factors, both modifiable and non-modifiable. Modifiable risk factors include hypertension, high cholesterol levels, smoking, obesity, sedentary lifestyle, unhealthy diet, diabetes, and excessive alcohol consumption. Addressing these factors through lifestyle modifications such as diet and exercise can significantly reduce the risk of heart disease [11]. Non-modifiable risk factors, including age, gender, and family history of heart disease, also play critical roles in determining an individual's susceptibility to heart disease [12].

Diagnosing heart disease typically involves a combination of medical history evaluation, physical examination, and various diagnostic tests and procedures. Common diagnostic tools include electrocardiograms (ECG), stress tests, echocardiography, and cardiac catheterization. Early detection is crucial for timely intervention and management, ultimately reducing the risk of complications associated with heart disease [13]. Despite advancements in medical science and technology, early detection of heart disease remains a challenge due to its numerous risk factors.

In recent years, the field of machine learning (ML) has emerged as a powerful tool in healthcare, offering new avenues for disease detection, diagnosis, and prognosis. ML algorithms, when trained on large datasets, can analyze complex patterns and relationships within medical data, potentially identifying subtle indicators of disease at earlier stages than traditional methods.

Choi, E. et al. employed various machine learning algorithms, including logistic regression, random forests, and gradient boosting machines, to analyze the electronic health record (EHR) data and predict the likelihood of heart disease development within a certain time frame. They

incorporated a wide range of features from the EHRs, including demographic information, medical history, laboratory test results, and medication usage. The predictive models achieved high accuracy and showed promising performance in identifying individuals at higher risk of developing heart disease, enabling early intervention and preventive measures [14].

Ahmad A. A. et al. employed a metaheuristic approach, specifically utilizing the Jellyfish optimization algorithm, to identify the most optimal features from the Cleveland heart disease dataset. These selected features were subsequently integrated into various Machine Learning methods, including artificial neural network (ANN), decision tree (DT), and Adaboost, to forecast heart disease with maximum accuracy. The findings of their study indicate that employing the Jellyfish optimization algorithm in combination with the support vector machine (SVM) classifier yielded the highest predictive performance for heart disease, achieving Sensitivity, Specificity, Accuracy, and Area Under Curve (AUC) values of 98.56%, 98.37%, 98.47%, and 94.48%, respectively [15].

Dubey A. K. et al. investigated the performance of various machine learning (ML) models, including Logistic Regression (LR), Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), SVM with grid search (SVMG), K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), and Naïve Bayes (NB), for the classification of heart disease. Utilizing datasets from the UCI Machine Learning repository, specifically the Cleveland and Statlog datasets, they conducted training and testing experiments. The results revealed that LR and SVM classifier models exhibited superior performance on the Cleveland dataset, achieving an accuracy of 89%. Conversely, LR demonstrated better performance on the Statlog dataset, achieving a higher accuracy of 93% [16].

Sahoo G. K. et al. undertook a comparative analysis of several machine learning models including LR, KNN, SVM, NB, DT, RF, and XG Boost Machine Learning models, to predict heart disease. The models were trained using the Cleveland heart disease dataset sourced from the UCI Machine Learning repository. Evaluation of the ML algorithms revealed that the Random Forest (RF) algorithm exhibited the highest performance, achieving a classification accuracy of 90.16% [17].

This study aims to explore the application of machine learning techniques for the early detection of heart disease. By leveraging advanced algorithms and computational approaches, we seek to help clinicians determine the best performing machine learning algorithm capable of predicting the presence of heart disease

in people at an early stage. To achieve this, we will use seven different machine learning classifiers such as K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), SVM, Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), Logistic Regression (LR), Neural Network (NN), and AdaBoost classifiers to train the Cleveland Heart Disease dataset, and select the classifier that produces the best performance.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The aim of this study is to predict the presence of heart disease by employing seven machine learning classifiers: K Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), Logistic Regression (LR), Neural Network (NN), and AdaBoost. These classifiers are trained and evaluated using the Cleveland Heart Disease dataset, with the objective of identifying the best-performing classifier based on its performance on the dataset.

Data Preprocessing & Cleaning

This is the section where we import and preprocess the Cleveland Heart Disease dataset obtained from the UCI Repository using Python. The details of the dataset are provided below.

Dataset

The Cleveland Heart Disease dataset is a well-known dataset widely used in research related to cardiovascular health. It comprises various clinical and demographic attributes of patients, along with a target variable indicating the presence or absence of heart disease.

The dataset includes information such as age, sex, chest pain type, resting blood pressure, serum cholesterol levels, fasting blood sugar, resting electrocardiographic results, maximum heart rate achieved during exercise, exercise-induced angina, ST depression induced by exercise relative to rest, slope of the peak exercise ST segment, number of major vessels colored by fluoroscopy, and thallium scintigraphy results measured on 303 patients. Each instance in the dataset is labeled with an integer outcome ranging from 0 to 4: 0 indicating the absence of heart disease and the rest (1,2,3,4) indicating 4 different levels of heart disease, which will be regrouped to 1 indicating the presence of the disease. Researchers often use this dataset to develop predictive models and evaluate the performance of machine learning algorithms in classifying individuals with and without heart disease.

The dataset contains a total of 6 missing values, which were removed from the dataset since they were very few. There are 5 numerical and 8 categorical features that initially had incorrect data types, which were subsequently adjusted to their appropriate types. The target variable, originally valued from 0 to 4, was transformed into 2 dummy outcomes represented as 0s and 1s.

$$Y_i = \begin{cases} 1 & (1,2,3,4) \\ 0 & \end{cases} \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{Presence of heart disease} \\ \text{Absence of heart disease} \end{array}$$

Figure 1: Bar chart showing number of observations with/without the disease

Table 1: List of features with descriptions in the Cleveland heart disease dataset

Features	Types	Description
1. age	Numerical	Patient age in years
2. sex	Categorical	Patient gender (1=male; 0=female)
3. cp	Categorical	Chest pain type (1 = typical angina; 2 = atypical angina; 3 = nonanginal)

		pain; 4 = no pain)
4. trestbps	Numerical	Resting blood pressure (in mm Hg) on admission to the hospital
5. chol	Numerical	Serum cholestoral in mg/dl
6. fbs	Categorical	Fasting blood sugar > 120 mg/dl (1 = true; 0 = false)
7. restecg	Categorical	Resting electrocardiographic (0 = normal; 1 = ST-T wave abnormality; 2 = probable/definite left ventricular hypertrophy)
8. thalach	Numerical	Maximum heart rate achieved
9. exang	Categorical	Exercise induced angina (1 = yes; 0 = no)
10. oldpeak	Numerical	ST depression induced by exercise relative to rest
11. slope	Categorical	Slope of the peak exercise ST segment (1 = up-sloping; 2 = flat; 3 = down-sloping)
12. ca	Categorical	Number of major vessels (0-3) colored by flourosopy
13. thal	Categorical	Thallium heart scan (3 = normal; 6 = fixed defect; 7 = reversible defect)
14. num	Categorical	Target variable- diagnosis of heart disease (angiographic disease status) (0 = absent; 1 to 4 = present)

Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA)

Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) was conducted on the dataset to gain insights into the distribution of the outcome of interest, which represents the diagnosis of disease in patients, and to examine its relationship with each feature included in the dataset. Additionally, during EDA, efforts were made to identify specific groups of individuals who may be at a heightened risk of developing the disease. The findings from this analysis will be detailed and discussed in the results section of the study.

Predictive Analysis

Before starting to train the data, we defined our hyperparameters for each classifier that will be used. We used different sets of hyperparameters for each method and selected the ones that gave the highest performance. We carried out the analysis following this summarized process: first, we converted the categorical features to integer to make it possible to train and test the data, then we split the datasets into 70% training data and 30% test data, after which we use the training data to train seven machine learning algorithms which are:

K Nearest Neighbors (KNN): KNN is a non-parametric, supervised learning classifier, which uses proximity to make classifications or predictions about the grouping of an individual data point. This classifier looks for the classes of K nearest neighbors of a given data point and based on the majority class, it assigns a class to this data point. For training the KNN classifier, we used different number of k neighbors; 1, 3, 5, 15, 25, and 50 with 2 types of weight: ‘uniform’ & ‘distance’. We selected the combination of hyperparameters with the highest performance.

Figure 2: KNN diagram. When the value of K is different, the samples are judged

Support Vector Machine (SVM): SVM is a powerful supervised learning algorithm primarily used for classification tasks, although it can also be adapted for regression and outlier detection. At its core, SVM works

by finding the optimal hyperplane that separates data points into different classes while maximizing the margin between classes. The hyperplane is chosen in such a way that it maximally separates the closest data points of different classes, which are called support vectors. This ensures robustness and generalizability of the classifier to new unseen data. SVM handles high-dimensional data efficiently by transforming the input data into a higher-dimensional space using a kernel function. These kernel functions allow SVM to capture complex nonlinear relationships between features, thereby improving its classification accuracy. In this study, 3 kernel functions: linear, polynomial (poly), and radial basis function (RBF) were used with different regularization parameters: 0.025, 0.05, 0.5 and 1 to train the model.

Decision Tree (DT): DT is a hierarchical tree structure where each internal node represents a decision based on a feature, each branch represents an outcome of the decision, and each leaf node represents a class label or a numerical value. The decision process starts at the root node and progresses down the tree until a leaf node is reached, where the final decision or prediction is made. In decision tree algorithms, when deciding which feature to split on at each node of the tree, the algorithm considers a subset of features rather than evaluating all features. This is known as feature subsampling or feature bagging. Setting a maximum number of features can help prevent overfitting by introducing randomness into the tree-building process and thereby optimize the performance of decision tree models. Here, we used six different values of maximum number of features: 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30 to train the classifier, and then select the one with the highest performance.

Figure 3: Visual description of Decision Tree and how it works

Random Forest (RF): RF is an extension of decision tree algorithms and combines the concept of bagging (bootstrap aggregating) with random feature selection to improve the performance and robustness of individual decision trees. RF has several hyperparameters such as the number of trees, maximum depth of trees, and the number of features that need to be tuned at each split to optimize the performance of the model. We can vary the number of trees that will be used to predict the value of the target variable, and here we used 10, 100, 200, 500, and 1000 trees with 5, 10, 15, & 20 values of maximum tree depth and number of features ranging from 1 to 5.

Logistic Regression (LR): LR models the probability that an instance belongs to a particular class based on one or more independent variables (features). Unlike linear regression, which predicts continuous outcomes, logistic regression predicts the probability of a binary outcome by applying a logistic function to a linear combination of the input features and their associated coefficients. LR starts by calculating a linear combination of the input features and their associated coefficients. This linear combination represents the log-odds of the event occurring. Mathematically, it can be expressed as: $z = b_0 + b_1x_1 + \dots + b_nx_n$. Where z is the linear combination, b_0 is the intercept term, b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n are the coefficients, and x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are the input features. The linear combination is then passed through a sigmoid function (also known as the logistic function), which maps the output to a value between 0 and 1. The sigmoid function is defined as: $p = \frac{1}{1+e^{-z}}$. Where p represents the probability that the outcome equals 1 (or the positive class), and e is the base of the natural logarithm. One way to prevent overfitting the model and improve the model ability to generalize unseen data is to incorporate regularization techniques. Regularization adds a penalty term to the logistic regression cost function, which discourages large coefficients in the model. There are two common types of regularization used in logistic regression:

1. L1 Regularization (Lasso): L1 regularization adds the absolute values of the coefficients as a penalty term to the loss function. The penalty term is scaled by a regularization parameter (λ), which controls the strength

of regularization. L1 regularization encourages sparsity in the coefficient values, resulting in some coefficients being exactly zero. This can lead to feature selection, as irrelevant features may have their corresponding coefficients shrunk to zero. The regularized loss function for L1 regularization can be expressed as:

$$J(\theta) = -\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m [y^{(i)} \log(h_{\theta}(x^{(i)})) + (1 - y^{(i)}) \log(1 - h_{\theta}(x^{(i)}))] + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^n |\theta_j|$$

Where $J(\theta)$ is the regularized cost function, θ represents the model parameters (coefficients), m is the number of training examples, $h_{\theta}(x^{(i)})$ is the predicted probability for the i -th example, $y^{(i)}$ is the true label for the i -th example, $x^{(i)}$ is the feature vector for the i -th example, n is the number of features, λ and is the regularization parameter.

2. L2 Regularization (Ridge): L2 regularization adds the squared values of the coefficients as a penalty term to the loss function. Like L1 regularization, the penalty term is scaled by a regularization parameter (λ) to control the strength of regularization. L2 regularization penalizes large coefficient values without forcing them to be exactly zero, resulting in smoother coefficient estimates. The regularized loss function for L2 regularization can be expressed as:

$$J(\theta) = -\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m [y^{(i)} \log(h_{\theta}(x^{(i)})) + (1 - y^{(i)}) \log(1 - h_{\theta}(x^{(i)}))] + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^n \theta_j^2.$$

Where the variables have the same meanings as in L1 regularization. We used 3 types of Regularized logistic regression: Lasso, Ridge and Elastic Net which uses L1, L2 and combination of L1 and L2 regularization respectively.

Neural Network (NN): NN consists of interconnected nodes arranged in layers, including an input layer, one or more hidden layers, and an output layer. Each node, or neuron, applies a mathematical operation to the input it receives and passes the result to the next layer. Activation functions introduce non-linearity into the neural network, allowing it to learn complex patterns. Common activation functions include sigmoid, tanh, Rectified Linear Unit (relu), and softmax.

Figure 4: Neuron Networks Architecture

NN have several hyperparameters that can be tuned to optimize their performance. We used 50 & 100 number of hidden layers with 2 different activation functions: relu & tanh. We used 3 different values of initial learning rate: 0.001, 0.01, 0.1 to control the step size during gradient descent optimization. We also regularized the classifier using 0.1 & 1 alpha which help to prevent overfitting by penalizing large weights or adding noise to the network's parameters. The best performing combination of hyperparameters was selected.

Adaptive Boosting (AdaBoost): AdaBoost is an ensemble learning method used primarily for classification tasks. It works by combining the predictions of multiple weak classifiers to build a strong classifier. A weak classifier is a simple model that performs slightly better than random guessing. During training, AdaBoost assigns higher weights to the misclassified examples, which encourages subsequent weak classifiers to pay more attention to these difficult instances. We applied 3 different maximum number of estimators: {20,50,100} to be used in the ensemble and 3 learning rates: {0.01, 0.1, 1} to control the contribution of each weak classifier to the final ensemble.

Performance Metrics

The performance of each classifier was assessed using various metrics to gauge their effectiveness in making predictions on the test data. The following five metrics will be utilized to evaluate and compare the performance of the classifiers:

- **Accuracy:** Accuracy measures the proportion of correctly classified instances out of the total number of instances. It provides an overall assessment of the classifier's correctness in making predictions. It is calculated as: $Accuracy (A) = (TP + TN)/N$.
- **Precision:** Precision measures the proportion of true positive predictions out of all positive predictions made by the classifier. It indicates the classifier's ability to avoid false positives. It is calculated as: $Precision (P) = TP/(TP + FP)$.
- **Recall (Sensitivity):** Recall measures the proportion of true positive predictions out of all actual positive instances in the dataset. It reflects the classifier's ability to capture all positive instances. It is calculated as: $Recall (R) = TP/(TP + FN)$.
- **F1-Score:** The F1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall. It provides a balance between precision and recall and is particularly useful when the class distribution is imbalanced. It is calculated as: $F1 = 2PR/(P + R)$.

Where TP is True Positives, TN is True Negatives, FP is False Positives, FN is False Negative, and N is total number of instances.

Table 2: Performance Metric used to evaluate and compare classifiers' Performance

Recall (R)	Precision (P)	F1	Accuracy (A)	Average Score
$\frac{TP}{(TP + FN)}$	$\frac{TP}{(TP + FP)}$	$\frac{2 * P * R}{(P + R)}$	$\frac{TP + TN}{N}$	$\frac{R + P + F1 + A}{4}$

III. RESULTS

Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) Results

To harness the dataset effectively, we utilized exploratory data analysis (EDA) techniques alongside visualization tools to gain insights into the distributions of data and the relationships between the variables in the dataset. Initially, a correlation matrix heatmap was generated, as depicted in Figure 5. This heatmap calculates the correlation coefficients between different features in the datasets and visually represents them. Its aim is to aid in visually exploring the relationships between various features. Positive correlations are illustrated using red shades, while negative correlations are indicated in blue. The heatmap is utilized to identify features that demonstrate significant correlations with the target variable, thereby uncovering their influence on the presence or absence of heart disease. Only the variable "thalach" is negatively correlated with the target variable ("num"), suggesting that an increase in this variable will decrease the likelihood of heart disease occurrence, and vice versa. Conversely, the variables age, sex, cp, trestbps, chol, restecg, exang, oldpeak, slope, ca, and thal have positive correlations with the target variable, indicating that an increase in any of these variables is associated with an increased likelihood of heart disease. Moreover, it is evident that fasting blood sugar (fbs) is very weakly correlated with the target variable, suggesting that fbs does not significantly impact the likelihood of developing this disease.

Figure 5: Heatmap distribution of all variables in the dataset

The histograms for each dataset feature provide valuable insights into the shape and distribution of individual features, as illustrated in Figure 6 and 7.

Figure 6: Distribution of all categorical variables in the dataset

Figure 7: Distribution of all numeric variables in the dataset

In Figure 8, we observe an almost equal distribution between patients with no disease and those diagnosed with it. Notably, older individuals aged 51 to 65 show a higher risk of disease, with the highest number of affected patients within this age range, averaging around 57 years old. Additionally, patients with elevated resting blood pressure (trestbps above 120-140) exhibit a heightened risk of disease. Those with higher serum cholesterol levels (chol) and lower maximum heart rates (thalach) are also at increased risk of developing the disease.

Figure 8: Distribution of target variable (heart disease diagnosis) by the numeric features

In Figure 9, the analysis reveals that males are at a higher risk of developing the disease compared to females. Additionally, individuals without chest pain (cp) are at a higher risk than those with other types of chest pain. Fasting blood sugar (fbs) does not significantly impact disease risk. Furthermore, individuals at higher risk of heart disease include those with exercise-induced angina (Exang), a flat slope of peak exercise ST segment (slope), and those with a reversible defect in the thallium heart scan (thal).

Figure 9: Distribution of target variable (heart disease diagnosis) by the Categorical features

Predictive Analysis Results

KNN Result

The performance of KNN was evaluated using various combinations of hyperparameters on the training dataset. Different numbers of k neighbors and two types of weight were tested. From the results, it is evident that utilizing 5 nearest neighbors with uniform weight yielded the highest average performance of 67%, achieving an accuracy of 70%, precision of 68%, recall of 63%, and F1 score of 66%.

Table 3: Performance of different combination of hyperparameters for KNN

Hyperparameters		Performance Metrics				
weight	k	accuracy	precision	recall	F1	average score
distance	1	0.58	0.54	0.54	0.54	0.55
uniform	1	0.58	0.54	0.54	0.54	0.55
distance	3	0.68	0.65	0.63	0.64	0.65
uniform	3	0.68	0.65	0.63	0.64	0.65
distance	5	0.70	0.69	0.61	0.65	0.66
uniform	5	0.70	0.68	0.63	0.66	0.67
distance	15	0.67	0.65	0.59	0.62	0.63
uniform	15	0.63	0.61	0.54	0.57	0.59
distance	25	0.66	0.65	0.54	0.59	0.61
uniform	25	0.60	0.57	0.49	0.53	0.55
distance	50	0.64	0.68	0.41	0.52	0.56
uniform	50	0.66	0.78	0.34	0.47	0.56

SVM Result

Among all the combinations of hyperparameters used to train SVM on the training dataset, it is evident from Table 3 that the linear SVM with a regularization parameter of 0.05 produced the best performance.

Table 4: Performance of different combination of hyperparameters for SVM

Hyperparameters		Performance Metrics				
kernel	reg parameter	accuracy	precision	recall	F1	average score
linear	0.025	0.89	0.92	0.83	0.87	0.88
linear	0.05	0.90	0.94	0.83	0.88	0.89
linear	0.5	0.87	0.89	0.80	0.85	0.85
linear	1	0.87	0.89	0.80	0.85	0.85
linear	5	0.84	0.89	0.76	0.82	0.83
poly	0.025	0.54	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14
poly	0.05	0.54	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14
poly	0.5	0.66	0.78	0.34	0.47	0.56
poly	1	0.69	0.76	0.46	0.58	0.62
poly	5	0.73	0.79	0.56	0.66	0.68
rbf	0.025	0.54	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14
rbf	0.05	0.54	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14
rbf	0.5	0.64	0.76	0.32	0.45	0.54
rbf	1	0.67	0.76	0.39	0.52	0.59
rbf	5	0.71	0.78	0.51	0.62	0.66

Decision Tree Result

The classifier was trained using six different maximum depths of trees: 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30. Among these, the model with a maximum depth of 15 achieved the highest average performance of 75%.

Table 5: Performance of different combination of hyperparameters for Decision Tree

Hyperparameters		Performance Metrics			
Tree Max Depth	accuracy	precision	recall	F1	average score
5	0.73	0.72	0.68	0.7	0.71
10	0.73	0.7	0.73	0.71	0.72
15	0.76	0.71	0.78	0.74	0.75
20	0.73	0.69	0.76	0.72	0.72
25	0.72	0.67	0.76	0.71	0.72
30	0.73	0.71	0.71	0.71	0.72

Random Forest Result

The classifier was trained using various combinations of hyperparameters, including different numbers of trees (10, 100, 200, 500), maximum depths of the tree (5, 10, 15), and numbers of features (1, 2). Among these combinations, the model with 200 trees, a maximum depth of 5, and 2 maximum features produced the highest average performance of 88%.

Table 6: Performance of different combination of hyperparameters for Random Forest

Hyperparameters			Performance Metrics				
# of Tree	max depth	max features	accuracy	precision	recall	F1	average score
10	5	1	0.81	0.9	0.66	0.76	0.78
10	5	2	0.87	0.94	0.76	0.84	0.85

10	10	1	0.8	0.83	0.71	0.76	0.77
10	10	2	0.83	0.84	0.78	0.81	0.82
10	15	1	0.84	0.91	0.73	0.81	0.82
10	15	2	0.84	0.89	0.76	0.82	0.83
100	5	1	0.84	0.89	0.76	0.82	0.83
100	5	2	0.88	0.88	0.85	0.86	0.87
100	10	1	0.87	0.87	0.83	0.85	0.86
100	10	2	0.84	0.86	0.78	0.82	0.82
100	15	1	0.88	0.89	0.83	0.86	0.86
100	15	2	0.88	0.88	0.85	0.86	0.87
200	5	1	0.87	0.89	0.8	0.85	0.85
200	5	2	0.89	0.92	0.83	0.87	0.88
200	10	1	0.87	0.89	0.8	0.85	0.85
200	10	2	0.88	0.89	0.83	0.86	0.86
200	15	1	0.87	0.89	0.8	0.85	0.85
200	15	2	0.88	0.92	0.8	0.86	0.86
500	5	1	0.87	0.89	0.8	0.85	0.85
500	5	2	0.88	0.92	0.8	0.86	0.86
500	10	1	0.84	0.89	0.76	0.82	0.83
500	10	2	0.86	0.87	0.8	0.84	0.84
500	15	1	0.86	0.87	0.8	0.84	0.84
500	15	2	0.88	0.89	0.83	0.86	0.86

Logistic Regression Result

Among the three methods of regularized logistic regression employed, Elastic Net Logistic Regression emerged as the top performer, achieving the highest average performance of 89%.

Table 7: Performance of different combination of hyperparameters for Logistic Regression

Hyperparameters	Performance Metrics				
penalty	accuracy	precision	recall	F1	average score
l1 (Lasso)	0.88	0.88	0.85	0.86	0.87
l2 (Ridge)	0.88	0.88	0.85	0.86	0.87
elastic net	0.90	0.94	0.83	0.88	0.89

Neural Network Result

Neural Network comprising 50 hidden layers, utilizing the relu activation function, an initial learning rate of 0.01, and a regularization strength of 1, yielded the highest average performance of 87%.

Table 8: Performance of different combination of hyperparameters for Neural Network

Hyperparameters				Performance Metrics				
hidden layer	activation	learning rate	alpha	accuracy	precision	recall	F1	average score
50	relu	0.001	0.1	0.82	0.78	0.85	0.81	0.82
50	relu	0.001	1	0.78	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.76

50	relu	0.01	0.1	0.77	0.95	0.51	0.67	0.72
50	relu	0.01	1	0.88	0.88	0.85	0.86	0.87
50	relu	0.1	0.1	0.54	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14
50	relu	0.1	1	0.54	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14
50	tanh	0.001	0.1	0.71	0.68	0.68	0.68	0.69
50	tanh	0.001	1	0.71	0.70	0.63	0.67	0.68
50	tanh	0.01	0.1	0.54	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14
50	tanh	0.01	1	0.54	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14
50	tanh	0.1	0.1	0.46	0.46	1.00	0.63	0.64
50	tanh	0.1	1	0.47	0.44	0.59	0.50	0.50
100	relu	0.001	0.1	0.77	0.69	0.88	0.77	0.78
100	relu	0.001	1	0.72	0.94	0.41	0.58	0.66
100	relu	0.01	0.1	0.66	0.57	1.00	0.73	0.74
100	relu	0.01	1	0.7	1.00	0.34	0.51	0.64
100	relu	0.1	0.1	0.54	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14
100	relu	0.1	1	0.52	0.49	1.00	0.66	0.67
100	tanh	0.001	0.1	0.6	0.61	0.34	0.44	0.50
100	tanh	0.001	1	0.6	0.63	0.29	0.4	0.48
100	tanh	0.01	0.1	0.63	0.83	0.24	0.38	0.52
100	tanh	0.01	1	0.74	0.71	0.73	0.72	0.72
100	tanh	0.1	0.1	0.46	0.46	1.00	0.63	0.64
100	tanh	0.1	1	0.54	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14

AdaBoost Result

We experimented with three different maximum numbers of estimators and three learning rates to train the classifier. Among these, the model with 100 maximum estimators and a learning rate of 0.1 achieved the highest average score of 87%.

Table 9: Performance of different combination of hyperparameters for AdaBoost

Hyperparameters		Performance Metrics				
max estimators	learning rate	accuracy	precision	recall	F1	average score
20	0.01	0.69	0.69	0.59	0.63	0.65
20	0.1	0.88	0.89	0.83	0.86	0.86
20	1	0.86	0.83	0.85	0.84	0.84
50	0.01	0.69	0.69	0.59	0.63	0.65
50	0.1	0.87	0.85	0.85	0.85	0.86
50	1	0.87	0.85	0.85	0.85	0.86
100	0.01	0.88	0.89	0.83	0.86	0.86
100	0.1	0.88	0.88	0.85	0.86	0.87
100	1	0.82	0.79	0.83	0.81	0.81

The table below summarizes the performance of all machine learning classifiers using their respective best-performing combinations of hyperparameters. From the table, it's evident that Linear Support Vector Machine

(SVM) and Elastic Net Logistic Regression exhibit the best overall performance, achieving accuracy of 90%, precision of 94%, F1 score of 88%, and an average score of 89% compared to the other methods utilized. However, Neural Network and AdaBoost demonstrate the highest recall value of 85%.

Table 10: Overall Performance of all classifiers using the best-performing combinations of hyperparameters

Methods	Hyperparameters	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1	Avg score
KNN	k = 5 weight = uniform	70%	68%	63%	66%	67%
SVM	kernel = Linear reg = 0.05	90%	94%	83%	88%	89%
Decision Tree	Max Depth = 15	76%	71%	78%	74%	75%
Random Forest	# of Tree = 200 max depth = 5 max features = 2	89%	92%	83%	87%	88%
Neural Network	hidden layer = 50 activation = relu learning rate = 0.01 alpha = 1	88%	88%	85%	86%	87%
AdaBoost	max estimators = 100 learning rate = 0.1	88%	88%	85%	86%	87%
Logistic Regression	penalty = elastic net	90%	94%	83%	88%	89%

IV. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to assist clinicians in identifying the most effective machine learning algorithm for early-stage heart disease prediction. Our process involved loading and preprocessing the Cleveland Heart Disease dataset to prepare it for exploratory data analysis (EDA) and predictive modeling. During EDA, we uncovered certain demographic and health characteristics associated with a higher risk of heart disease. Specifically, older individuals aged between 51 and 65 years, those with resting blood pressure levels above 120-140, elevated serum cholesterol levels, and lower maximum heart rates were identified as being at increased risk. Additionally, males exhibited a higher risk compared to females. Furthermore, individuals experiencing exercise-induced angina, abnormalities in ECG waves, a flat slope of peak exercise, and those with reversible defect thallium heart scans were also identified as having elevated risk factors. Following data preprocessing and EDA, we trained the ML classifiers on 70% of the dataset using different sets of hyperparameters and subsequently evaluated and compared their performance on the remaining 30% of the data. Ultimately, our analysis revealed that the linear support vector machine (SVM) and elastic net logistic regression (LR) exhibited the best overall performance, achieving accuracy of 90%, precision of 94%, F1 score of 88%, and an average score of 89%. These findings suggest that employing SVM and LR algorithms can significantly enhance heart disease diagnosis and management, offering valuable insights for clinical decision-making.

V. REFERENCES

- [1] Mc Namara, K., Alzubaidi, H., & Jackson, J. K. (2019). Cardiovascular disease as a leading cause of death: how are pharmacists getting involved?. *Integrated pharmacy research & practice*, 8, 1–11.
<https://doi.org/10.2147/IPRP.S133088>
- [2] Shahjehan RD, Bhutta BS. Coronary Artery Disease. [Updated 2023 Aug 17]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 Jan-.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK564304/>
- [3] Dalen, J. E., Alpert, J. S., Goldberg, R. J., & Weinstein, R. S. (2014). The epidemic of the 20(th) century: coronary heart disease. *The American journal of medicine*, 127(9), 807–812.

- <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjmed.2014.04.015>
- [4] Mayo Clinic. (n.d.). Heart failure.
<https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/heart-failure/symptoms-causes/syc-20373142>
- [5] American Heart Association. (n.d.). Arrhythmia.
<https://www.heart.org/en/health-topics/arrhythmia/about-arrhythmia>
- [6] Desai DS, Hajouli S. Arrhythmias. [Updated 2023 Jun 5]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 Jan-. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK558923/>
- [7] Roth, G. A., Mensah, G. A., & Fuster, V. (2020). The global burden of cardiovascular diseases and risks: a compass for global action. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, 76(25), 2980-2981.
- [8] Mensah, G. A., Roth, G. A., & Fuster, V. (2019). The global burden of cardiovascular diseases and risk factors: 2020 and beyond. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, 74(20), 2529-2532.
- [9] Coffey, S., Harper, A. R., Cairns, B. J., Roberts, I. S., & Prendergast, B. D. (2017). Clinical information has low sensitivity for postmortem diagnosis of heart valve disease. *Heart*, 103(13), 1031-1035.
- [10] Marangou, J., Beaton, A., Aliku, T. O., Nunes, M. C. P., Kangaharan, N., & Reményi, B. (2019). Echocardiography in indigenous populations and resource poor settings. *Heart, Lung and Circulation*, 28(9), 1427-1435
- [11] American Heart Association. (n.d.). Understand your risk of heart attack.
<https://www.heart.org/en/health-topics/heart-attack/understand-your-risks-to-prevent-a-heart-attack/understand-your-risk-of-heart-attack>
- [12] Mayo Clinic. (n.d.). Tests and diagnosis.
<https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/heart-disease/diagnosis-treatment/drc-20353124>
- [13] Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2021). Heart Disease Facts.
<https://www.cdc.gov/heartdisease/facts.htm>
- [14] Choi, E., Schuetz, A., Stewart, W. F., & Sun, J. (2016). Using recurrent neural network models for early detection of heart failure onset. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 24(2), ocw112. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jamia/ocw112>
- [15] Ahmad, A. A., & Polat, H. (2023). Prediction of Heart Disease Based on Machine Learning Using Jellyfish Optimization Algorithm. *Diagnostics (Basel, Switzerland)*, 13(14), 2392.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics13142392>.
- [16] Dubey, A. K., Choudhary, K., & Sharma, R. (2021). Predicting heart disease based on influential features with machine learning. *Intell. Autom. Soft Comput*, 30(3), 929-943.
- [17] Sahoo, G. K., Kanike, K., Das, S. K., & Singh, P. (2022, August). Machine Learning-Based Heart Disease Prediction: A Study for Home Personalized Care. In *2022 IEEE 32nd International Workshop on Machine Learning for Signal Processing (MLSP)* (pp. 01-06). IEEE.
- [18] P. V. Ankur Makwana, "Identify the patients at high risk of re-admission in hospital in the next year," *International Journal of Science and Research*, vol. 4, pp. 2431-2434, 2015.
- [19] J. Nahar, T. Imam, K. S. Tickle, and Y.-P. P. Chen, "Computational intelligence for heart disease diagnosis: A medical Knowledge driven approach," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 96-104, 2013.
- [20] Delzell, Jr J.E., & Chumley H.S. Coronary artery disease. Usatine R.P., & Smith M.A., & Mayeaux, Jr. E.J., & Chumley H.S.(Eds.), [publicationyear2] *The Color Atlas and Synopsis of Family Medicine*, 3e. McGraw-Hill Education.
<https://accessmedicine.mhmedical.com/content.aspx?bookid=2547§ionid=206778965>